

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Selenium(IV) by N-Bromosuccinimide

L. S. A. DIKSHITULU, P. VANI and B. VASANTHA KUMAR

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair-530 003

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The kinetics of oxidation of Se(IV) by N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) has been studied in 0.1 M perchloric acid medium. The order with respect to NBS is unity whereas that with respect to Se(IV) varies between one and two depending on the [Se(IV)]. Increase in ionic strength as well as [H⁺] causes a decrease in the rate of the reaction. Br⁻ also retards the reaction considerably. Molecular bromine has been shown to be the actual oxidising species involved in the reaction. Dimeric Se(IV) has been found to be considerably more reactive than the monomeric form. E_a and ΔS[‡] for the path involving monomeric Se(IV) are 26.0 ± 0.9 k cal mole⁻¹ and 22.2 ± 3.0 cal mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹, respectively.

RECENTLY, we have reported the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of Se(IV) by N-chlorosuccinimide (NCS)¹ in hydrochloric acid medium. We have now taken up a kinetic study of the oxidation of Se(IV) by N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in acid medium, with a view to compare the mechanism of oxidation of Se(IV) by the two N-haloimides. Interestingly, it has been noticed that the oxidation of Se(IV) by NBS is much faster than by NCS, although the latter is normally a more powerful oxidising agent than the former.

Experimental

0.2 M solutions of Se(IV) and Se(VI) were prepared by dissolving sodium selenite (BDH, LR) and sodium selenate (BDH, AR) in water, respectively and their strengths checked by iodometric method. A 0.01 M aqueous solution of NBS was prepared before use from recrystallised sample of NBS (BDH, LR) and its strength verified iodometrically. A 0.1 M solution of succinimide was prepared by dissolving recrystallised sample of succinimide (BDH, LR) in water. A 0.1 M solution of bromine water was prepared by shaking bromine (E. Merck, pure) with water. Its strength was determined iodometrically before use and a 0.01 M solution was prepared from it by suitable dilution. All other chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade.

Kinetics procedure: It was observed that in the absence of Br⁻ there was no reaction between NBS and Se(IV). However, in the presence of Br⁻ the reaction between Se(IV) and NBS was found to proceed uniformly at a measurable rate. In view of this observation, all investigations were carried out in the presence of a ten fold excess of Br⁻ compared to [NBS]. Unless otherwise mentioned, the kinetic runs were carried out in 0.1 M perchloric

acid medium at a constant temp. of 25 ± 0.1° keeping the concentrations of Se(IV) and H⁺ in considerable excess over that of NBS, and maintaining a constant ionic strength of 1.0 M. NBS on being mixed with Br⁻ in acid medium, gives rise to an yellow coloured solution of Br₂ which attains maximum absorbance immediately on mixing. The progress of the reaction is monitored using a Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer at 400 nm, where aqueous Br₂ has nearly maximum absorbance and all other species involved in the reaction have negligible absorbance. The pseudo-first order rate constants calculated from the slopes of log (absorbance) vs time plots were represented by k' and were found to be reproducible within ± 3%.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry: A known excess of NBS was allowed to react with a known [Se(IV)] in 0.1 M HClO₄ medium in presence of 5-10 fold excess of [Br⁻]. After applying a small blank correction for the self decomposition of NBS, the stoichiometry of the reaction was found to correspond to the equation

Effect of ionic strength: The influence of ionic strength on the rate of the reaction was studied by varying the ionic strength with sodium perchlorate from 0.2 M to 1.2 M, keeping the concentrations of all other species constant. The pseudo-first order rate constants were found to decrease with increase in ionic strength (Table 1).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF IONIC STRENGTH ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k'

[NBS] = 5.0×10^{-4} M; [Se(IV)] = 2.0×10^{-3} M;
[Br⁻] = 5.0×10^{-3} M; [H⁺] = 0.1 M; $t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$

μ , M(NaClO ₄)	0.2	0.4	0.6	0.8	1.0	1.2
$10^4 k' \text{ sec}^{-1}$	19.4	17.8	16.7	15.8	14.8	13.5

Effect of products : Even a 20 fold excess of the products, Se(VI) or succinimide, do not have any effect on the rate of the reaction.

Effect of Br⁻ : Since the reaction between Se(IV) and NBS has been found to proceed only in the presence of Br⁻, the effect of [Br⁻] on the rate of the reaction was studied. It was found that log[NBS] vs time plots were straight lines only when [Br⁻] was two fold or more as compared to [NBS]. Further increase in [Br⁻] was found to retard the reaction considerably (Table 2). This may be due to the conversion of Br₂ into much less reactive Br₃⁻.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF [Br⁻] ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k'

[NBS] = 5.0×10^{-4} M; [Se(IV)] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; [H⁺] = 0.1 M;
 $t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄)

[Br ⁻] $\times 10^3$, M	2.0	3.0	5.0	10.0	20.0	25.0	30.0
$10^4 k' \text{ sec}^{-1}$	19.8	17.8	14.8	11.0	6.5	5.5	4.6

Order with respect to NBS : The fact that the plots of log[NBS] vs time were straight lines even beyond 70% completion of the reaction indicates that the reaction is first order in NBS. Further, the pseudo-first order rate constants were found to remain constant at different [NBS] (Table 3) confirming the order with respect to NBS to be unity.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF [NBS] ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k'

[Se(IV)] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; [Br⁻] = 5.0×10^{-3} M; [H⁺] = 0.1 M;
 $t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄)

[NBS] $\times 10^4$, M	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5	15.0	20.0
$10^4 k' \text{ sec}^{-1}$	14.8	15.1	14.6	15.1	15.3	14.6

Order with respect to Br₂ : Since the reaction between Se(IV) and NBS proceeds only in presence of Br⁻, it may be presumed that Br₂ is the actual oxidising species involved in the reaction. In order to verify this, kinetic runs were carried out with bromine water of the same concentration as NBS, and the log[Br₂] vs time plots were found to be straight lines indicating the order with respect to Br₂ to be unity. Also k' values at different [Br₂] were found to be constant (Table 4).

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF [BROMINE WATER] ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k'

[Se(IV)] = 2.0×10^{-3} M; [Br⁻] = 5.0×10^{-3} M; [H⁺] = 0.1 M;
 $t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄)

[Br ₂] $\times 10^4$, M	5.0	7.5	10.0	12.5	15.0	20.0
$10^4 k' \text{ sec}^{-1}$	15.1	15.5	15.3	15.8	15.1	15.3

A comparison of the k' values presented in Tables 3 and 4 shows that the rates of oxidation of Se(IV) by NBS and by bromine water are in very good agreement, thus supporting the contention that Br₂ is the actual oxidising species involved in the oxidation of Se(IV) by NBS.

Order with respect to Se(IV) : In view of the well known dimerisation of Se(IV) in aqueous acidic media², we have carried out a detailed study of the effect of [Se(IV)] on the rate of the Se(IV)-NBS reaction with a view to determine the reactivities of both monomeric and dimeric Se(IV). Kinetic runs were carried out varying the [Se(IV)] over a wide range [0.003 to 0.04 M, where the extent of monomeric Se(IV) varies from 97 to 75%], keeping the concentrations of all other species constant. The order with respect to Se(IV) was found to be one at lower concentrations (upto 0.01 M) where Se(IV) is predominantly in the monomeric form. At higher [Se(IV)] (>0.01 M) the order with respect to Se(IV) was found to lie between one and two. A similar observation was made by earlier workers during a kinetic study of the oxidation of Se(IV) by Np(VII)³ and chloramine-T⁴.

From the observed mixed order kinetics it may be inferred that both monomeric and dimeric Se(IV) are kinetically reactive. The dependence of the pseudo-first order rate constant, k' , on [Se(IV)] may therefore be expressed by equations (1) and (2).

$$k' = k_m[\text{Se(IV)}_m] + k_d[\text{Se(IV)}_d] \quad \dots (1)$$

$$= k_m[\text{Se(IV)}_m] + k_d D[\text{Se(IV)}_m]^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

where $D = [\text{Se(IV)}_d]/[\text{Se(IV)}_m]^2 \quad \dots (3)$

or $\frac{k'}{[\text{Se(IV)}_m]} = k_m + k_d D[\text{Se(IV)}_m] \quad \dots (4)$

Equation (4) indicates that the plot of $k'/[\text{Se(IV)}_m]$ vs $[\text{Se(IV)}_m]$ should be linear with an intercept on the rate axis, and from the magnitudes of intercept, slope and the dimerisation constant, D, ($D = 5.6 \pm$

Fig. 1. Plot of $k'/[\text{Se(IV)}_m]$ vs $[\text{Se(IV)}_m]$. [NBS] = 5.0×10^{-4} M; [H⁺] = 0.1 M; [Br⁻] = 5.0×10^{-3} M; $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄); $t = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ$.

1.0 M⁻¹ at 25° and μ=1.0 M NaClO₄) the values of k_m and k_a were calculated. The variation of rate with varying [Se(IV)] was studied at 25° and the results shown in Fig. 1. The rate constants of the monomer and dimer at 25° were computed from Fig. 1 and found to be $(5.26 \pm 0.10) \times 10^{-2}$ and $(42.8 \pm 1.2) \times 10^{-2}$ l mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹, respectively. From these values it may be seen that dimeric Se(IV) is considerably more reactive than the monomeric form, as was already observed in Se(IV)-Np(VII)³ and Se(IV)-chloramine-T⁴ reactions.

Effect of [H⁺]: To study the effect of [H⁺] on the rate of the reaction kinetic runs were carried out at different [H⁺] and the pseudo-first order rate constants were found to decrease with increase in [H⁺] (Table 5).

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF [H⁺] ON THE PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, k'

[H ⁺], M	0.05	0.07	0.10	0.15	0.20	0.25	0.3
10 ⁴ k' sec ⁻¹	80.6	36.0	14.8	5.3	3.4	1.8	1.3

Mechanism: The dissociation constant of selenous acid⁵ is 3.0×10^{-8} at 25° and μ=1.0 M (NaClO₄) from which it may be computed that under the present experimental conditions (0.1 M HClO₄), 97% of Se(IV) shall be present as H₂SeO₃ and the remaining 3% as HSeO₃⁻.

The possible species of NBS in acid medium are NBS, NBSH⁺ and Br⁺. However, since there is no direct reaction between NBS and Se(IV), none of these species can be presumed to be reactive in the present investigation. NBS on being mixed with Br⁻ ion gives rise to a yellow coloured solution of molecular bromine, the absorbance of which reaches a maximum value immediately.

This molecular bromine is the actual oxidising species involved in the oxidation of Se(IV) by NBS. This presumption is supported by the observation that the k' values for the oxidation of Se(IV) by NBS and bromine water of the same concentration are in very good agreement (Tables 3 and 4).

In view of these observations the following mechanism has been proposed

This mechanism leads to the rate equation

$$\frac{d[\text{NBS}]}{dt} = \frac{k_1[\text{NBS}][\text{Se(IV)}_m] + k_2[\text{NBS}][\text{Se(IV)}_a]}{1 + K[\text{Br}^-]} \quad \dots (10)$$

At very low concentrations (< 0.005 M) since Se(IV) exists predominantly in the monomeric form, $[\text{Se(IV)}_m] \approx [\text{Se(IV)}]$; hence the second step in equation (10) may be neglected and rearranged to give the equation

$$\frac{1}{k'} = \frac{1}{k_1[\text{Se(IV)}]} + \frac{K[\text{Br}^-]}{k_1[\text{Se(IV)}]} \quad \dots (11)$$

Equation (11) predicts that the plot of $1/k'$ vs $[\text{Br}^-]$ should be a straight line with an intercept on the rate axis, the intercept corresponding to $1/k_1[\text{Se(IV)}]$ (Fig. 2). From the magnitude of the intercepts at 20, 25, 30 and 35° the values of k_1 [i.e. rate constants of the rate-determining step for the path involving monomeric Se(IV)] are determined and found to be 5.8×10^{-2} , 11.1×10^{-2} , 24.5×10^{-2} and 50.0×10^{-2} l mol⁻¹ sec⁻¹, respectively. From these rate constants, E_a and ΔS^\ddagger are computed to be 26.0 ± 0.9 kcal mol⁻¹ and 22.2 ± 3.0 cal mol⁻¹ deg⁻¹, respectively.

Fig. 2. Plots of $1/k'$ vs. $[\text{Br}^-]$ at different temp. $[\text{NBS}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4}$ M; $[\text{Se(IV)}] = 5.0 \times 10^{-3}$ M; $[\text{H}^+] = 0.1$ M; $\mu = 1.0$ M (NaClO₄). (1) 293K, (2) 298K, (3) 303K and (4) 308K.

Further, from equation (10) it may be seen that the rate should be independent of [H⁺]. However, experimental results show that the pseudo-first order rate constants decrease with increase in [H⁺]. This may be attributed to the conversion of HSeO₃⁻ of

greater nucleophilicity into much less nucleophilic H_2SeO_3 , as the $[H^+]$ is increased, or as the acid concentration is increased the dimer may get progressively dissociated into the less reactive monomer, which might also be a factor contributing to the decrease in rate.

Although, NCS is normally a more powerful oxidising agent than NBS, a comparison of the rates of oxidation of Se(IV) by the two oxidants shows that the latter oxidizes Se(IV) much more rapidly than the former. A similar observation⁷ was also made in the oxidation of alcohols and it was suggested that the difference in reactivity between NCS and NBS is probably due to the fact that the halogen in the NBS molecule ($>N^{\delta-}-Br^{\delta+}$) is more positive than that in NCS and the easier protonation of NBS makes the rupture of N—Br bond more facile than that of the N—Cl bond. Thus, while Br_2

is formed almost instantaneously from NBS and Br^- , Cl_2 is formed only slowly from NCS and Cl^- which explains the difference in the rates of oxidation of Se(IV) by the two oxidants.

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